

People with Disabilities (PWD) and Inclusion at Workplace: A Case study on employees of Pizza Hut, Thimbirigasaya

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Abstract

Inclusion at workplace has today become a contemporary buzz which leads the need for enabling diverse social strata to be a part of the corporate world. One such key social category are the people with disabilities (PWDs) specially in a developing country like Sri Lanka where the corporate inclusion is vital in the long run. This research study aims to identify how people with disabilities and inclusion at workplace assessed through key elements of relationship, shared experience and transparency. The research design followed positivism through a deductive reasoning approach in order to conduct a quantitative study following a mono-method by undertaking a case study approach. The cross-sectional study was conducted using a questionnaire as the primary data collection method. The study population is employees at Pizza Hut, Thimbirigasaya where a sample of 24 employees were taken following simple random sampling technique. The data analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS statistical data processing where the relationship between the variables were assessed using the Pearson correlation and Chi-square tests. According to the statistical results, a strong positive relationship was identified between shared experience and inclusion of people with disabilities (PWDs) while a moderate positive relationship was identified between relationships and transparency with inclusion of people with disabilities (PWDs). These findings align with the former research literature reinforcing the need for focus on inclusion of people with disabilities (PWDs). Further, the study recommends to the existing body of knowledge necessity to create supportive work environment, sense of belongingness, interaction with other employees, proper team and work performance measures and effective communication and equity at workplace to ensure success.

Keywords: Inclusion, People with Disabilities, Shared experience, Transparency

1. Introduction

1.1. Background of the Study

This study intends to assess Pizza Hut's diversity, equity, and inclusion programs, particularly as they relate to employees with disabilities. We could further look into a number of topics,

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including hiring practices, employee training, workplace accommodations, professional development opportunities, and general assistance given to employees with disabilities, by conducting a case study at Pizza Hut in Thimbirigasaya. The results of this study will provide insight into how well Pizza Hut's inclusive environment initiatives work for people with disabilities. Additionally, the study may examine how inclusive practices affect the performance, general well-being, and job satisfaction of employees with disabilities. Other companies trying to improve their assistance for workers with disabilities can learn a lot from Pizza Hut's commitment to diversity and inclusion for people with impairments.

1.2. Research Objectives

The main aim of this research is to identify how Pizza hut's in Thimbirigasaya is getting benefited by having a new skill set of people who face disabilities. In order to conduct the study the following research objectives have been formulated.

RO1: To identify the influence of relationship at workplace for People with disabilities (PWD)

RO2: To identify the shared experience between People with disabilities (PWD) and other employees.

RO3: To identify the transparency of management towards People with disabilities (PWD) at Workplace.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

According to former research, people with disabilities faced significant disadvantages in the job market when it came to their ability to integrate into the economy through work this also made them to move away from social life (Colella, et al., 2005). According to the research of Mkhize, (2018), all people with disabilities (PWD) must be mandatorily educated from their childhood till their highest level in order to gain a good exposure to the corporate working environment. This Study in Zimbabwe also revealed that 35% of the children not getting graduated from their primary

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education to the post primary which in result affects their employment opportunities in future. In the competitive labor market in Sri Lanka, 8.6% of the total population are differently abled peoples and out of them 29.4% are the people who are employed (Department of Census and Statistics, 2012). Offering them job opportunities and empowering them will motivate and minimize all of their problems that they face.

2.2. Inclusion

Inclusion as a theme of Corporate Social Responsibility has different opinion by different parties, social inclusion is an opportunity given to the people who has faced disadvantages in their life (Suarez, et al., 2015) However, according to World Bank, (2013) The process of enhancing a person's capacity, opportunity, and dignity to participate in society on the basis of their identity is known as social inclusion. Corporate inclusion efforts aim to educate underprivileged groups about health and wellness practices, as well as to train and employ marginalized populations, including women without formal education, individuals with physical disabilities, and ethnic minorities. One of the key components of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) that promotes equality and innovation in the workplace is inclusion.

2.3. Inclusion in food and beverage industry

The food and beverage industry which is one of the competitive sector in the world is facing so many labor turnovers every day with 100%, According to the words of Hafi, (2019) India is facing 166 – 170% turnovers every months, which means a guy who is working at the outlet would be not available after three weeks of time.

2.4. Differently abled people / People with Disabilities (PWD)

Disability is the social isolation brought about by a society's reaction to people with disabilities, even though an impairment can be a physical ailment or functional constraint. (Joesph, 2007). According to estimates from the World Health Organization (2022) 16% of global population is facing a disability which has affected their daily lifetime routines. Individuals who have disabilities are more likely to have unfavorable socioeconomic consequences, including lower levels of

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education, worse health outcomes, lower employment rates, and higher rates of poverty. Moreover, a large number of disabled individuals have unmet medical needs that render them extremely vulnerable. According to Karunaratne, (2021) Sri Lanka has a significant number of disabled individuals; the 2011 population census found that 8.7% of the country's overall population met these criteria. Over 1.6 million people are included in this, with a somewhat higher percentage of men (57%) than women (43%).

2.5. Interconnection of Key Elements of inclusion with People with Disabilities (PWD)

Relationship

Fostering an inclusive culture requires that the components of the inclusion relationship with individuals with disabilities are interconnected. Disability inclusion demands more than just encouragement; it also calls for efficient policies and procedures to guarantee participation in a range of responsibilities and activities. However, according to McKinney & Swartz, (2019) Individuals with disabilities encounter obstacles throughout the integration stage of their job.

Shared experience

According to Verulava & Bedianashvili, (2021) Employers' ethical standards govern the connection with individuals with impairments; legal regulations do not govern it. Still if the government provides certain tax benefits to employers, they should be more encouraged to hire people with disabilities (PWD).

Transparency

The way that components of inclusion transparency relate to individuals with disabilities highlights how crucial it is that social structures acknowledge and deal with exclusion. A study and research done by Lindsay, et al., (2019) stated that the interview conducted among eleven females and six males resulted showing the timing of when the youth would disclose their disability to their employer, and it would also depend on the level of comfort and type of the job along with industry.

2.6. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework; Source: (Johari, et al., 2022)

2.7. Hypotheses

Ha1: There is a relationship between relationship and inclusion of people with disabilities

Ha2: There is a relationship between shared experiences and inclusion of people with disabilities

Ha3: There is a relationship between transparency and inclusion of people with disabilities

3. Methodology

The research study is focused on the assessment of people with disabilities and inclusion at work in a chosen food franchise in Sri Lanka. In order to conduct the study the research follows positivism focused on the elaboration of objective and quantifiable data. The deductive reasoning is selected as the research approach where the formulation of the hypothesis is done based on the existing theories in order to conduct the study. The study follows a quantitative study approach followed by a mono-quantitative approach using the case study design. As survey method is followed using questionnaires using the five-point Likert Scale to gather the primary data and the study adopts cross sectional time horizon. The secondary data collection is done using peer-reviewed journals, articles and other credible source utilization. The study adopted simple random sampling and to gathered data from a sample of 24 respondents. The data analysis follows a content analysis where IBM SPSS is used for the statistical data processing with discussion on both descriptive and inferential statistics.

4. Data Analysis

4.1. Reliability

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

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Reliability Statistics		
Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Relationship	.785	4
Shared Experience	.889	4
Transparency	.895	4

As the table of the reliability statistics provided based on the Cronbach's Alpha with twelve statements on the people with disabilities and inclusion at work questionnaire the values were 0.785, 0.889 and 0.895 respectively for relationship, shared experience and transparency. As the $0.7 < \alpha > 1$ the index is considered to be highly reliable and accepted and shows the internal consistency of the measurements.

4.2. Inferential analysis

Table 2: Inferential Statistics Table

Inferential Statistics Analysis		
Independent Variable	Pearson Correlation	Remarks
Relationship	0.346	Moderate positive relationship
Shared Experience	0.658	strong positive relationship
Transparency	0.547	Moderate positive relationship
Chi-square testing		
Independent Variable	Chi - Square	Remarks
Relationship	0.000	Alternative Hypothesis accepted
Shared Experience	0.000	Alternative Hypothesis accepted
Transparency	0.000	Alternative Hypothesis accepted

As the inferential statistics summary provided, the Pearson correlation value indicated a positive relationship between the independent variables; the relationship, shared experience and

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transparency with the dependent variable; people with disabilities. The relationship and people with disabilities showcase a value of 0.346 a moderate positive relationship and chi-square test as p value <0.05 it rejects the null hypothesis accepting the alternative hypothesis. The results presented by Grzeškowiak, et al., (2021), in their research conducted to analyze the inclusion factor between employees working as people with disabilities (PWDs) has a positive correlation.

The shared experience and people with disabilities showcase a value of 0.658 a strong positive relationship and chi-square test as p value <0.05 it rejects the null hypothesis accepting the alternative hypothesis. The results presented by Santilli, et al., (2023), in their research conducted to analyse the sense of belonging factor between employees with disabilities on shared experiences had a positive correlation. The same results presented by Romeo, et al., (2020), in their research conducted for people with disabilities (PWDs) in Barcelona Spain where the shared experience had a positive correlation with general commitment and exchange, affective and values.

The transparency and people with disabilities showcase a value of 0.547 a moderate positive relationship and chi-square test as p value <0.05 it rejects the null hypothesis accepting the alternative hypothesis. The results presented by Brzykcy & Boehm, (2022), in their research conducted to analyse the interaction factor people with disabilities (PWDs) and transparency has a positive relationship.

5. Recommendations

Foster a supportive environment at workplace that promotes the people with disabilities (PWD) that will increase the interaction between them positively and contribute towards the organisations success.

Provide a sense of belonging through the shared experience and employee empowerment in making sense of belonging impactful decision between employees working as people with disabilities (PWDs).

Promote people with disabilities (PWDs) and other employees to interact at work with safe working conditions and interactive work breakdown that enhance the manner in which people interact.

Promote the work performance and team performance between employees working as people with disabilities (PWDs) and non-disabled employees to improve in the long run.

Follow transparent communication, equity at workplace and enable the work setting to allow the people with disabilities (PWDs) to align their career goals with the corporate setting.

6. Conclusion

The research study identified a contemporary social requirement to focus on the people with disabilities (PWDs) and inclusion at workplace; undertaken by the case study on Pizza Hut Thimbirigasaya, Sri Lanka. The study used relationships, shared experience and transparency as key independent variables to derive its relationship with inclusion of people with disabilities (PWDs). As the result findings through Pearson correlation and chi-square tests provided the study identified a strong positive relationship between shared experiences and inclusion of people with disabilities (PWDs). While a moderate positive relationship was identified between relationship and transparency inclusion of people with disabilities (PWDs). This denotes the increasing trend of identification of people with disabilities (PWDs) in corporate setting allowing them to work better with proper work environments. While the study results were consistent in nature there were both time and scope limitations. In order to enhance the internal validity, it is important that future research efforts focus on a larger sample size and a longitudinal time horizon.

7. References

Brzykcy, A. & Boehm, S., 2022. The impact of disability labels on relationship building at work.. *Human relations*, 75(4), pp. 734-763.

Colella, A., Stone, D. L. & Dipboye, R. L., 2005. *Discrimination at Work*. 1 ed. New York: Psychology Press.

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Copyright ♥ authors 2025

691

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Department of Census and Statistics, 2012. *Disability in Sri Lanka*, Sri Lanka: Department of Census and Statistics.

Grześkowiak, A., Załuska, U., Ciotucha, D. K. & Kozyra, C., 2021. People with Disabilities in the Workplace: Results of a Survey Conducted among Polish and Finnish Employers. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(20), pp. 1-14. doi: 10.3390/ijerph182010934

Hafi, F. R., 2019. Outlet manned by people with disabilities, a world's first for the brand. *Daily FT*, 04 June.

Joesph, K. A., 2007. Implementing the social model of disability. *International sociology review of books*, 22(2), pp. 247-250.

Karunaratne, R. R., 2021. A Brief Review of Disability Rights and Welfare in Sri Lanka. *Sri Lanka Journal of Social Development*, 1(7), pp. 1-66. doi:10.4038/sljsd.v1i2.20

Lindsay, S., Cagliostro, E., Leck, J. & Shen, W., 2019. Disability disclosure and workplace accommodations among youth with disabilities. *Disability and Rehabilitation*, 41(16), pp. 1914-1924. doi: 10.1080/09638288.2018.1451926

McKinney, E. & Swartz, L., 2019. Employment integration barriers: Experiences of people with disabilities. *International journal of Human Resource Management*, 1(1), pp. 1-23. doi: 10.1080/09585192.2019.1579749

Mkhize, T. J., 2018. *THE ASSESSMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL INCLUSION IN THE EMPLOYMENT OF DIFFERENTLY ABLED PEOPLE (DAP): A CASE STUDY OF THE SOUTH AFRICAN SOCIAL SECURITY AGENCY IN KWAZULU NATAL*, South Africa: University of KWAZULU NATAL.

Romeo, M., Baldo, M. Y. & Lins, C., 2020. *Job Satisfaction and Turnover intention among people with disabilities working in special employment centers: The moderation effect of organizational commitment*, Barcelona: Frontiers in Psychology.

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692

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Santilli, S., Ginevra, M. C. & Nota, L., 2023. Colleagues' Work Attitudes towards Employees with Disability. *European Journal of Investigation in Health. Psychology and Education*, 13(1), pp. 130-140. doi:10.3390/ejihpe13010009

Suarez, E. et al., 2015. CSR: Does It Foster Inclusion and Diversity? An Exploratory Study in the Ibero-American Countries. *Academy of Management Proceedings*, 1(1), pp. 1 - 21.

Verulava , T. & Bedianashvili, G., 2021. Work Inclusion of Person with disabilities: Employer's Perspective. *Quality Access to Success*, 22(182), pp. 159-163.

World Bank, 2013. *World Bank*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/>
[Accessed 24 02 2024]

World Health Organization, 2022. *Global report on health equity for persons with disabilities*, United States: World Health Organizations.